

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6374252>

THE SHRINE OF “O’SMAT OTA” - CULTURAL HERITAGE

Kenjaev Abduvali Shuhrat o’gli

English teacher at school number 1 in Bakhmal district, Jizzakh region

Annotation: *In the developing world tourism is becoming the most valuable and invested sector. Improvement of shrines and sanctuaries, development of tourism and domestic tourism have become one of the most urgent tasks today. Understanding history will eventually help raise morally, strengthen culture and most importantly increase pride in the spirit of the nation.*

Keywords: *Pilgrimage tourism, Jizzakh region, location, O’smat ota, legend, Baxmal, mountains, Abdulhamid ibn Xusayn and family trees.*

In the center of the Bakhmal region, near Kurgantepa, there is a beautiful place - "Osmat Ota" - a shrine. Historical objects and archaeological materials confirm that the tumor appeared earlier, at the beginning before Christ. Bakhmal writer Sayyid Azim, based on historians Olimjon and Jaloliddin Juraev, associates the tomb of Osmata Otu with the name of Abul Fatah Muhammad ibn Abdukhamid Osmandi as-Samarkandi, a scholar of Osh and a prominent lawyer of his time. Abul Fath Osmandi was born in 1095 and died in 1158 at the age of 63.

His book "Sharh al-Jami al-Kabir", written in Arabic and consisting of several volumes, has been preserved. We are talking about Imam Usmani Turkestani, who lived in the late 16th and first half of the 15th century. Here it is better to understand the nickname "Turkestan" not "Turkestan" but "Turkestan" - "Mountain Turkestan", unlike the mountains Zaamin and Bakhmal, which are called "homeland of the Turks".

The patron saint Osmani was a colleague of his Turkestan contemporary Hazrat Bashir. Hazrat Bashir, who was originally a bookworm, is known to have lived in Sangzora with the Dervish authorities for some time. According to Hazrat Bashir's history textbook, Hazrat Bashir and his teacher, Usmani, will go barefoot to Turkestan to visit Haji Ahmad Yassawi. They see a lot of problems along the way. When they got to Firor (the former name of the village of Aulia), they asked one of the houses for permission: "Let's warm up a little knife in the oven."

"Hazrat Sheikh Buzrukvar (Hazrat Bashir) said, 'When my eyes fell asleep, I had a dream. In my dream, Sayyid Ahmad Yasawi said, "Oh, my son, accepting the suffering of

ordinary people is dear to Allah." When I woke up, I told my dream to Master Osman. Uthman said: "The tombs of Hadrat Sadri Baba (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) are nearby. She has children, elders and disciples. Let's go there and tell the story. "We visited the tombs of Sadri Babu.

In particular, Master Osman is a man who has earned the rank of Turkestan saint. Hazrat Sheikh Buzrukvar said, "Whoever comes to visit me should first visit Hazrat Usmani Turkestani."

Hazrat Bashir was born in 1379 AD and it is known that Hazrat "Usman" Usman was older than Hazrat Sheikh Buzrukvar, a young saint from Turkestan.

O'smat ota Shrine is located in the center of the Bakhmal region, surrounded by well-ventilated mountain springs with an area of half a hectare. It is currently used for recreational and recreational purposes.

The second possibility belongs to Farrukh Akchaev, who believes: Ustrushana, the Jizzakh oasis, is today one of the holiest cities and is located along the Great Silk Road, which has connected east and west since ancient times. His role in the development of science and the rise of culture is very great. Below is a description of the shrine of Osmat and the scientist named after him, one of the most famous scientists of the medieval Muslim East (illustrated by articles by Otabek Muhammadiev, head of the publishing department of the Imam Bukhari International Center) style temple.

One of the outstanding children of the Ustrushana oasis is undoubtedly the well-known lawyer and scholar of his time, the thinker Muhammad ibn Abdulkhamid Usmandi Samarkandi. The full name of the scientist is Abdufat Alauddin Muhammad ibn Abdulhamid ibn Umar ibn Hasan ibn Hussein Usmandi Samarkandi and various sources contain information about the year of his birth and death. According to some sources, "Alloma was born in Samarkand in 408/1017 and died there in 502/1109."

Sources state that Abulfat Muhammad ibn Abdulhamid ibn Hussein ibn Hasan ibn Hamza Usmandi, a native of Samarkand, was known as the "pillar of the universe." Written sources claim that there is much controversy as to whether the place where the scientist was born and raised was called "Asmand" or "Usmand". Some scientists say that this place was called Asmand and the scientist was called Asmand, others the village of Usmand and another Samand.

In our opinion, the village where the scientist was born was called "Usmand" because there is now a town called Osmat in Bakhmal district in the Jizzakh region, which has been restored by the efforts of many scientists. At the same time, it is known from history that the territory of the present-day Jizzakh region was previously part of ancient Samarkand.

Usmat is located 70 km west of Jizzakh, the regional center. There is also controversy over whether a scientist was named Asmandia or Osman, depending on where he was born.

As mentioned above, in some sources it is called Asmandiy and in most sources - Osmandi.

Abdulhamid ibn Umar Usmandi, the father of the scientist, was one of the leading scientists in Samarkand and was known among the people for his eloquence and eloquence. His full name is Abu Muhammad Abdulhamid ibn Umar ibn Husayn ibn Hasan ibn Hamza ibn Tahir Usmani and the sources only mention his name and the hadiths he spoke. No information is provided about his career or status during his term, or even the years of his birth or death.

Very little is known about the life of a scientist in written sources. They only mention that Alauddin Muhammad Usmandi died in Bukhara in 552/1157.

The scientist gained his knowledge of fiqh from his teacher Ashraf ibn Muhammad Alavi. Imam Ashraf al-Alawi received his fiqh education from his father Muhammad and passed it on to his father Abu Shuja. According to Samani, Judge Marwa Ghazi Muhammad ibn Utba Soyigi said this in his book Az-Zayl.

Imam Ashraf Alavi's father studied at Kusam ibn Abbas Madrasah in Samarkand. He went to Hijaz, became a pilgrim to Baghdad, and returned to Samarkand, where he taught and spread knowledge for the rest of his life. He died at Shawwal 491 AH at the age of 54 and was buried in the famous Chokardiz Cemetery in Samarkand. He learned the science of hadiths from Umar ibn Abdullah ibn Maz Bukhari, known as Sadrush Shahid. Among them are Hisomush Shahid, Sadrush Shahid, Safforush Shahid. He was a leading scholar in many Islamic sciences, especially in the sciences, hadiths and calamities, as well as in the study of the differences between the various sects. He was characterized by deep knowledge, unique talent and excellent potential in disputes and discussions between scientists in these fields. Therefore, he was known among scholars as noble nicknames as "Alouddin" (Pillar of Religion).

Based on the sources, it can be said with certainty that the most famous of the students who educated the scientist was Abdumuzaffar Jamal Islam Asad Karobisi. The Quraysh State states in its Jawahir al-Muzziya fi Tabaqat al-Hanafi (Brilliant Pearls on Scholars of the Order of Hanafi) and Ibn Qutlubo in its Tajut al-Tarajim (Crown of Biographies) that the full name of the scholar is Assad ibn Muhammad. . ibn Hussein al-Karabisi.-Islam "and is the author of the book" Al-furuk fil-masoil-firakiya "(Disagreements between sectarian questions). He gained legal knowledge from Alouddin Usmandi Samarkandi, Sayyid Ashraf and his father Sayyid Abu Shuja. Karobisi died in 570. Al-Furuk was published in Kuwait in 1982. The first volume says that Aluddin Muhammad ibn

Abdulhamid Usmandi Hanafi, who wrote a commentary on Umar Nasafir's Manzum, was one of Karabisi's teachers.

In addition, the author of the famous work "Al-Ansab" (Nasabnama), the famous Abdul Karim Samani (1113-1167), states in this work that "my son Muzaffar heard a hadith from him". There is also evidence that Sheikh al-Islam Nizamuddin Umar ibn Sheikh al-Islam Burhaniddin Ali ibn Abu Bakr Marginani, son of the great lawyer Burhanuddin Marginani (1123-1197), author of the famous work Al-Khidoyya, was also a student scientist.

In general, a comprehensive study of the life of the scientist and the rich scientific and spiritual heritage he left behind reaffirms that our country's scientists have made a significant and significant contribution to the development of Islamic culture and philosophy, especially Islamic sciences.

REFERENCES:

1. www.google.uz
2. www.tourism in jizzakx.uz
3. www.baxmal.jizzax.uz
4. O.Burguli.Tashkent 1996.
5. “O‘zbekiston ziyoratgohlari va qadamjolari” – B.Eraliyev, I.Ostonaqulov, N.Abdulohatov, Turon Zamin Ziyo, Toshkent 2014 yil.